

Can Data Centers Power an Energy Transformation on Alaska's Railbelt?

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April 2525

Suggested Citation:

P. Asmus, G. Holdmann, and E. Gudleifsson. "Can Data Centers Power an Energy Transformation on Alaska's Railbelt" Alaska Center for Energy and Power, University of Alaska, Fairbanks, 2525. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15176160

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Glossary of Abbreviations and Acronyms

ACEP	Alaska Center for Energy and Power
C&I	Commercial and Industrial
DC	Data Center
EIA	Energy Information Administration
kW	kilowatt
kWh	kilowatt hour
ms	milliseconds
MW	Megawatt
NATO	North Atlantic Treaty Organization

Executive Summary

Data centers are rapidly becoming the dominant driver of new electricity demand, with projections indicating that their growth may soon outpace the ability of utilities to deliver clean and reliable power at scale. After years of flat or declining demand in the power sector, there is now a sudden and urgent need to bring new capacity online—often at unprecedented speed—and to consider locating data centers outside traditional urban and industrial hubs.

The United States hosts over half of all data centers globally, emphasizing its central role in the digital economy. Can Alaska leverage its vast natural resources - including Arctic location - to become a viable frontier for data center innovation?

This brief explores Alaska’s potential role in the emerging data center economy through a three-part analysis. First, it provides background on the evolving data center landscape and its growing influence on electricity markets. Second, it examines how large-scale industrial load can contribute to lowering energy costs, drawing on examples from other sectors and regions, with a focus on a case study of Iceland. Finally, it considers what these dynamics mean for Alaska—highlighting both the state’s unique advantages and the challenges it faces in becoming a competitive data center hub.

To attract data centers as long-term industrial customers, Alaska may benefit from taking proactive steps to align energy development, infrastructure planning, and economic incentives with the needs of this rapidly growing, high-volume energy consumption sector. The following approaches could support this goal:

- Developing shovel-ready energy projects designed for scale

- Encouraging potential data center customers to evaluate total costs of operations—including cooling—rather than just local electricity rates
- Exploring synergies between data center operations and broader energy infrastructure
- Advancing co-location and grid optimization strategies through policymaker and regulatory collaboration

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1 Introduction

Data centers are rapidly becoming the dominant driver of new electricity demand, with projections indicating that their growth may soon outpace the ability of utilities to deliver clean and reliable power at scale. After years of flat or declining demand in the power sector, there is now a sudden and urgent need to bring new capacity online—often at unprecedented speed—and to consider locating data centers outside traditional urban and industrial hubs.

A 2024 [report](#) prepared by Lawrence Berkeley National Laboratory found that data center load growth has tripled over the past decade and is projected to double or triple again by 2028. Globally, data centers are estimated to consume 1 to 2% of total electricity demand; in the United States—where over half of all data centers are located—the share is even higher, estimated at [2 to 4% of national electricity consumption](#). As the geography of digital infrastructure begins to shift, we ask: What role—if any—could Alaska play in the evolving energy and data economy?

This brief explores Alaska’s potential role in the emerging data center economy through a three-part analysis. First, it provides background on the evolving data center landscape and its growing influence on electricity markets. Second, it examines how large-scale industrial load can contribute to lowering energy costs, drawing on examples from other sectors and regions, with a focus on a case study of Iceland. Finally, it considers what these dynamics mean for Alaska—highlighting both the state’s unique advantages and the challenges it faces in becoming a competitive data center hub.

Figure 1. Global Data Center Markets and Fiber Connectivity. This map highlights the top 10 global data center markets, overlaid on the international network of submarine fiber optic cables that enable digital connectivity. With more than [8,000 data centers](#) operating worldwide, robust fiber infrastructure remains a critical factor in siting and scaling data infrastructure. The United States hosts over half of all data centers globally, emphasizing its central role in the digital economy.

2 What Does the Future of Data Centers Look Like, and How Do We Power Them?

Data centers are specialized facilities that house computer servers and networking equipment to support a wide range of digital services, from cloud computing and artificial intelligence to content delivery and financial transactions. However, they are hardly monolithic. These facilities vary widely in form, design, and scale—ranging from hyper-scale campuses that consume hundreds of megawatts (MW) to small edge data centers operating at kilowatt (kW) scale. This diversity is often obscured by the hype surrounding aggregate energy demand, leading to misconceptions about the energy profile and infrastructure needs of any single data center.

At present, only two data centers are operating in Alaska:

- A colocation facility in Anchorage operated by the telco company [GCI](#), which provides 2.5 gigabyte residential Internet speeds to 80% of Alaskans. The data center is a modular design featuring self-contained pods to deliver onsite power and cooling.

- A small 150-kW edge data center developed by [Greensparc](#) running on 100% hydroelectricity installed within the [Cordova microgrid](#) and which came on-line this year.

Alaska could soon have another data center come on-line shortly, this one sharing features with Iceland in one way - it would serve bitcoin mining operations - but deviating in other ways, principally in its power supply and size. The application filed in November last year by [Hilcorp and TA Infrastructure](#) would allow the data center to operate in a shipping container over a four-year period. It would tap existing natural gas generators in the North Slope for its power supply, which researchers at the University of Alaska Fairbanks warn would emit substantial amounts of carbon emissions given the intense round-the-clock bitcoin mining process.

The [North Digital data center](#) proposed for Prudhoe Bay is also a modular design that hopes to tap regional gas reserves but seeks to reduce its environmental footprint. How? By relying upon clean-burning fuel cells for power generation coupled with carbon capture technologies. Utilizing the ambient cooling and cold water will reduce energy consumption by 40-60%, claims Far North Digital, the project developer. The project is dependent upon fiber cable connections currently under development to Tokyo and Ireland to serve overseas markets.

When it comes to data centers that fundamentally reshape how energy is produced and used within Alaska's primary power markets, it is the large-scale facilities that truly move the needle. These hyper-scale centers can serve as industrial baseload anchors—providing stable, long-term demand that could, in theory, justify investment in large-scale energy infrastructure that local demand alone may not support. As the industry searches for new sites with ample land and energy access, interest is expanding beyond traditional urban hubs in the continental U.S. Major players such as [Amazon, Meta, and Microsoft](#) are being courted to explore opportunities in Alaska.

In some ways, data centers represent a modern version of the industrial load centers that underwrote major energy infrastructure in the last century. Just as aluminum smelters and other heavy industries provided stable, long-term demand that justified the development of massive hydropower and nuclear projects, today's hyper-scale data centers have the potential to serve a similar function. Their consistent, around-the-clock energy needs can create a revenue foundation that helps reduce the per-unit cost of electricity for all users.

This effect stems from how fixed infrastructure costs are recovered in energy systems. When large industrial customers commit to long-term energy purchases, utilities or independent developers can spread fixed generation and transmission costs over more kilowatt-hours. This improves economies of scale and can lead to lower average rates for smaller consumers, including residential and commercial users. In regions like Alaska—where dispersed demand and high energy costs make infrastructure development challenging—anchoring new energy projects to large, steady consumers like data centers could offer a viable path toward system-wide cost reduction.

Iceland provides an illustrative example—not only in the realm of data centers, but also as a historical case study of how industrial anchor loads can support affordable power for society more broadly. Decades before attracting global tech companies, Iceland developed large-scale

hydropower projects to serve energy-intensive industries such as aluminum smelting. These industrial customers provided a stable financial base that justified major infrastructure investments, ultimately lowering the cost of electricity across the system. More recently, Iceland has leveraged the same principles—abundant renewable energy, stable base load customers, and long-term planning—to attract data center investments, demonstrating how targeted industrial development can align with national energy and economic goals.

3 Iceland as a Model: Lessons for Alaska’s Data Center and Energy Strategy

Iceland’s green energy accessibility and naturally cold climate—which significantly reduce cooling costs—have been key factors in attracting data center investments. The country’s push into digital infrastructure began in 2007 with the establishment of Verne Global, which repurposed land on a former NATO base to develop a data center campus powered entirely by renewable energy. Founded by Novator Partners and General Catalyst, the project aligned with Iceland’s long-term strategy of leveraging its abundant hydropower and geothermal resources to draw energy-intensive industries. Although Verne Global experienced a slow start—its first operational year was not until 2012—it has since become a flagship example of how strategic siting and clean energy can support digital infrastructure growth in remote regions.

Iceland’s first operational data center, however, was Thor Data Center, which opened in 2010 with an initial installed capacity of 2 MW. In a departure from conventional models that rely on national utilities, Thor sourced its electricity directly from an independent power producer (IPP). Specifically, it secured 3.2 megawatts of power from HS Orka, a renewable energy provider located on the Reykjanes Peninsula, with an option to expand capacity to 19.2 megawatts. In 2014, Thor expanded further by establishing a second facility with 12 MW of capacity, designed to serve the international cryptocurrency company [Bitfury](#).

From 2015 to 2022, electricity consumption by data centers in Iceland grew at an average annual rate of 44%, making them one of the fastest-growing components of the country’s energy landscape. By 2022, data centers accounted for approximately 7% of electricity consumption within Iceland’s commercial and industrial (C&I) energy sector. As of that year, Iceland hosted three large data centers officially classified as C&I energy-intensive users—defined under national law as consuming more than 80 GWh annually at a single site, or roughly 10 MW. This sustained growth has contributed to job creation and broader economic benefits.

Figure 2. Iceland’s aluminum smelter electricity loads as well as other C&I consumers have remained remarkably consistent over the past decade. In contrast, data center (DC) loads have jumped and are reaching about the same level of impact on the Iceland power grid as these other large consumers. Figures derived from Iceland’s energy authority: Orkustofnun (2023). OS-2023-T003-01: Electricity use in Iceland 2020-2022

The Icelandic data center industry primarily serves international markets, with direct fiber connections to the United Kingdom (including London and Dublin), Germany (Frankfurt, Munich, and Berlin), and the United States (San Francisco, Seattle, New York, Boston, and Washington, D.C.). Notably, approximately 95% of data center customers in Iceland are based overseas, underscoring the country’s role as a globally connected, export-oriented data infrastructure hub.

The growth of Iceland’s data center industry can be largely attributed to two key factors. First, the availability of curtailable load agreements made electricity more affordable and flexible for energy-intensive customers. These agreements allowed industrial users to purchase surplus electricity from Iceland’s installed generation capacity at reduced rates, offering a cost advantage that proved highly attractive to data center developers. Second, the industry’s expansion is closely aligned with the rise of the cryptocurrency sector. Crypto mining operations, in particular, benefited from the ability to quickly curtail energy use in response to grid conditions—an operational model well-suited to Iceland’s flexible energy offerings. Similar benefits from curtailable load agreements have also been observed in other industries, including district heating providers in cold regions reliant on diesel, and fish meal factories operating on heavy fuel oil.

Most data centers today do not participate in flexible load-shedding programs such as demand response. As a result, they often overinvest in on-site generation assets that remain idle much of the time, contributing to higher capital and operational costs. Microgrids—especially those with diverse energy assets and the capability to provide grid services—could offer a more efficient alternative. However, realizing this potential would require a cultural shift among data center operators, who have traditionally prioritized absolute reliability over flexibility. In this regard, Iceland’s experience could serve as a valuable model for utilities along Alaska’s Railbelt.

Reportedly, some data center developers in Iceland have used cryptocurrency mining operations as a form of bootstrap funding—leveraging their high tolerance for load curtailment to get early-stage facilities off the ground. In some cases, these crypto customers are phased out once longer-term clients with more stable demand profiles are secured. Although this approach is difficult to verify and has generated public debate in Iceland about the best use of the country’s renewable energy resources, it highlights the classic “chicken or egg” dilemma: should new generation be developed first, or should utilities wait for large customers to materialize before investing?

4 How Could Data Centers Lower Alaska’s Energy Costs?

Many large data center companies have set ambitious decarbonization targets, often going beyond current regulatory requirements. Providers such as Google and Microsoft have [partnered with the nuclear industry](#) to explore opportunities at sites once slated for decommissioning, as well as to assess the future role of small modular reactors (SMRs). Other operators are pursuing microgrids developed by private-sector entities that incorporate high penetrations of renewable energy. Whether through nuclear, advanced microgrids, or large-scale geothermal and hydroelectric projects, these companies are actively seeking clean, reliable electricity—and looking to move beyond the traditional diesel backup model.

While these corporate goals are clear, the national political climate creates some uncertainty around the trajectory of U.S. climate and energy policy. Nevertheless, many multinational data center operators are expected to remain committed to decarbonization, both to meet internal targets and to align with investor, customer, and international expectations—regardless of shifting federal priorities.

2.1 Alaska Advantages

Alaska has several advantages in attracting data centers, including the following:

- *Cold Climate Efficiency.* Like Iceland, Alaska benefits from a naturally cold climate that can significantly reduce the need for mechanical cooling in data centers. This not only improves energy efficiency but also lowers operating costs—an increasingly important factor for companies seeking to reduce both emissions and expenses. Passive cooling potential is one of Alaska’s most straightforward advantages.
- *Underutilized Generation Capacity (with Constraints):* Unlike many U.S. markets operating near capacity, parts of Alaska’s Railbelt grid still have underutilized generation capacity. This could, in theory, support new industrial loads such as data centers. However, much of this capacity is gas-fired, and the state faces long-term uncertainty around natural gas supply. Moreover, the availability of low-cost or rapidly deployable capacity is limited. While not a turnkey solution, this underutilization does suggest that Alaska may have a window of opportunity—especially if paired with new clean energy investments or flexible load strategies.

- *Free Cooling from Cold Climate:* One of Alaska’s most straightforward advantages is its naturally cold climate, which enables free or low-cost air-based cooling for data centers. Cooling typically accounts for about 5% of a data center’s ongoing operations and maintenance costs. While that may seem modest, for highly cost-sensitive operators, even small percentage savings can have a meaningful impact—especially when scaled across large, energy-intensive facilities. This is part of the reason why major providers, such as Google, [seek locations like Nevada](#) where 100% baseload geothermal power is available. However, unlike sites in warmer climates—including western Australia—Alaska offers a critical additional benefit: abundant access to natural cooling. This makes it particularly competitive for colocation with renewable generation. Iceland clearly shares this advantage, and it has played a key role in that country’s success in attracting international data center clients.
- *Untapped Renewable Energy Potential:* Alaska has significant renewable energy potential, both along the Railbelt and in more remote regions. On the Railbelt, wind, geothermal, and long-considered projects like the Susitna hydroelectric dam have been studied for decades. However, due to relatively low electricity demand and limited economies of scale, many of these projects have remained economically unjustifiable. Partnering with mega-scale data center operators—like the approach Iceland has taken—could provide the consistent industrial load needed to revisit or rethink these large-scale renewable projects.
- *Stranded Energy Resources:* Beyond the Railbelt, Alaska also holds vast quantities of stranded energy resources. These include renewable resources, such as geothermal in the Aleutians, and conventional ones, such as coal and natural gas, which remain undeveloped due to infrastructure limitations and lack of local demand. Strategically aligned development could unlock some of this potential—especially if paired with data centers that are flexible in siting and committed to clean or low-carbon energy sources.

One other potential advantage Alaska has in terms of attracting data centers is that the state has deployed [more microgrids than any other U.S. state](#), some running almost completely on carbon-free resources. Data centers require resilient and reliable energy supplies and are increasingly investigating microgrids to achieve these goals. The Railbelt Grid is composed of multiple interconnected microgrids which could serve as a fertile environment for new data center deployments (see map below).

Figure 3. Alaska’s Railbelt Grid Structure and Load-Capacity Profile. The Railbelt electric system is composed of several interconnected regional service areas, centered around three primary load balancing zones: the Kenai Peninsula, Anchorage/Mat-Su, and the Northern region. This diagram illustrates the winter peak demand relative to installed generation capacity across these areas, highlighting the variation in system headroom. While the Railbelt has some underutilized capacity, especially outside of peak winter periods, this distribution is uneven and depends heavily on local resource availability and infrastructure constraints.

2.2 Alaska Disadvantages

In addition to its strengths, Alaska faces several significant challenges in attracting data center investment—particularly around digital connectivity.

- Connectivity Constraints: Alaska as a Digital Cul-de-Sac.** Alaska sits at the terminus of the global internet backbone, with relatively few fiber connections linking it to the rest of the world, and many of these routes pass through a handful of key nodes (Figure 3). This lack of diverse routing introduces a single point of failure risk: damage to an undersea cable or failure at a key hub can result in significant outages. In fact, Alaska does experience regional connectivity disruptions on a not-infrequent basis, whether from physical damage to infrastructure or other technical issues. For industries requiring continuous, high-reliability data flow, this level of vulnerability can be a disincentive.
- Latency Constraints:** Alaska’s remote location also creates challenges related to latency—a key factor in determining the viability of certain data center applications. Latency refers to the time it takes for data to travel to a destination and back. For some real-time applications, even small delays can be a limiting factor. A representative with operations in both Iceland and Scandinavia noted that Icelandic data centers are unsuitable for some business uses due to latency. For example, one-way latency between Reykjavik and Frankfurt is about 18 milliseconds (ms), or at least 36 ms round trip. The distance between

Anchorage and Silicon Valley is similar—around 2,000 miles—suggesting that, like Iceland, Alaska is not ideal for latency-sensitive workloads such as generative AI or high-frequency trading. However, applications like cloud storage, batch processing, and archival services are far less sensitive to latency and may still be a strong fit—especially when paired with clean, low-cost power.

Figure 4. Connectivity Constraints: Alaska as a Digital Cul-de-Sac. This map shows Alaska’s limited integration into the global network of undersea fiber optic cables. Most international data traffic routes through a small number of landing points, with few redundant paths and minimal direct links to Asia. This lack of network diversity contributes to latency, reduces reliability, and creates single points of failure—factors that can limit the viability of latency-sensitive or high-availability data center applications in the state.

- *High Cost of Energy on the Railbelt.* Compared to the Top 10 U.S. data center markets, Alaska—particularly the Railbelt—faces a significant disadvantage when it comes to the cost of electricity. Other states benefit from lower-cost power driven by larger markets, diversified energy portfolios, and greater economies of scale. This presents a classic chicken-and-egg dilemma: large industrial loads, such as data centers, could help bring down electricity rates on the Railbelt by spreading fixed costs and supporting investment in advanced, lower-cost energy infrastructure. But those very loads are unlikely to materialize unless energy costs become more competitive to begin with. Without a strategic shift in how generation and pricing are approached, this cycle is difficult to break.

Figure 5. Energy Costs in the Top 10 U.S. Data Center Markets Compared to Alaska

This chart compares the number of data centers in the top 10 U.S. markets with commercial electricity rates, highlighting Alaska’s disadvantage in energy pricing. The red line indicates Alaska’s average commercial electricity rate (October 2023), while the blue dashed line shows the U.S. commercial average. Alaska’s electricity costs remain significantly higher than those in leading markets—posing a key barrier to attracting large-scale data infrastructure without structural change.

5 Next Steps and Opportunities: What Alaska Needs to do to Attract Data Center Loads

To attract data centers as long-term industrial customers, Alaska will need to take proactive steps to align energy development, infrastructure planning, and economic incentives with the needs of this rapidly growing high volume energy consumption sector.

Develop Shovel-Ready Energy Projects Designed for Scale

Alaska should prioritize advancing shovel-ready energy projects—particularly those that are slightly oversized or intentionally overbuilt to accommodate future industrial loads. These projects are most likely to move forward when they are already characterized, permitted, with preliminary designs completed, and are waiting for long-term investment partners or anchor customers. This approach mirrors Iceland’s successful model, where large-scale renewable infrastructure was developed in anticipation of future high-capacity users like data centers. By creating excess capacity, Alaska can offer data center operators dedicated clean power supplies while justifying infrastructure investments that are otherwise uneconomical under current local demand. Importantly, this approach should not be limited to renewables—nuclear energy,

including small modular reactors, could complement existing generation and serve as a long-term alternative to declining Cook Inlet natural gas resources.

Evaluate Total Cost of Operations, Not Just Electricity Rates

Though electricity rates in Alaska remain high relative to major U.S. data center markets, the state's cold climate provides an important offset by significantly reducing cooling costs. With cooling accounting for roughly 5% of ongoing operations and maintenance expenses for a typical data center, Alaska's climate advantage could shift the total cost of operations closer to competitive levels—particularly for applications tolerant of slightly higher latency.

Explore Synergies with Broader Energy Infrastructure

Some stakeholders see the data center industry as a potential anchor customer for large-scale infrastructure projects—such as a long-envisioned natural gas pipeline connecting the Anchorage and Fairbanks regions to North Slope reserves. Interest from cryptocurrency operators has recently revived discussion of using data center load growth to support pipeline development. Whereas natural gas is not ideal for data centers pursuing aggressive decarbonization goals, it could serve as a transitional fuel—offering firm capacity to support renewable integration and grid reliability. In the long term, this infrastructure could enable hydrogen or synthetic fuel production, positioning Alaska as both a digital and energy export hub.

Advance Co-Location and Grid Optimization Strategies

Data centers sited along the Railbelt could help accelerate decarbonization by increasing system load and enabling greater economies of scale. These facilities could take advantage of cold climate conditions and hydro resources for low-cost cooling while contributing to a more efficient and resilient electric grid. Hosting regional cloud services could also support the development of a secure grid architecture that integrates power, communications, and computing. Paired with the right policy reforms—including demand response and dynamic load management—this model could help optimize Railbelt operations and integrate new renewables more cost-effectively.

6 Conclusion: A Long-Term Opportunity to Redefine Alaska's Role in the Digital Economy

Hyper-scale data centers represent both an immediate opportunity and a long-term game changer for Alaska. In the near term, attracting such loads could lower electricity costs and support sustainable energy infrastructure. Over the longer term, data centers could help transform Alaska's position in the global digital landscape—from a perceived cul-de-sac at the top of the world into a strategic data exchange hub linking North America with fast-growing markets in the Asia-Pacific and perhaps even Europe as well.

The U.S. already leads the world in data center deployments, but viable new sites are becoming increasingly scarce. Alaska has its pros and cons—but with a clear short-term strategy and a phased, long-term development plan, the state can begin carving out a niche in this critical sector. Doing so would offer not only the chance to stabilize and reduce electricity costs, but to build a more resilient, clean, and globally connected energy future. For Alaska, focusing on data

center clients that are less sensitive to load disruptions could provide a lower-risk entry point into this emerging industrial sector. Though potentially controversial, such a strategy could represent a pragmatic first step.

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